

Research Data Management Plan (DMP) for EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the Epidemiological Profile of Oral Health in Latvian Children and Adolescents

Version 2

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EpiDentLatvia project describe the plan for managing, storing, sharing, and preserving data generated during the research. **EpiDentLatvia** targets the urgent oral health challenge in Latvia, where nearly all 12-year-olds are affected by dental caries. The project aims to generate evidence using traditional statistics and machine learning to identify risk factors, predict dental service needs and map inequalities in access. By analysing national and research datasets, it will inform policies that support prevention-focused, equitable dental care in line with WHO and UN health goals.

The primary objectives of this DMP are:

1. **Data Collection and Standardisation:** Establishing protocols for collecting data on various risk factors affecting dental health, accessibility of dental services, and the impacts of treatment disruptions, while ensuring standardisation across datasets for meaningful analyses.
2. **Data Sharing and Open Science Commitment:** The project emphasizes transparency and reproducibility by sharing cleaned and anonymized datasets in FAIR-compliant repositories. This commitment encourages public participation and collaboration with policymakers, aiming to democratize research tools.
3. **Data Analysis and Security:** Safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of research data while implementing robust statistical techniques and machine learning

methods for analysis, to identify trends, disparities, and predictive factors influencing oral health outcomes.

4. **Long-term Preservation:** Ensuring that all datasets can be accessed post-project completion for future research, policy formulation, and ongoing public health initiatives. This aligns with the overall goal of fostering a collaborative environment in oral health research.

Funder

RSU Internal and RSU with LASE
External Consolidation

Grant

EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the
Epidemiological Profile of Oral
Health in Latvian Children and
Adolescents

Researchers

Sergio Uribe (orcid:0000-0003-0684-2025), Ilze Maldupa
(orcid:0000-0002-5967-956X)

Organizations

Riga Stradiņš University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Research Data Management Plan \(DMP\) for EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the Epidemiological Profile of Oral Health in Latvian Children and Adolescents](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EpiDentLatvia project describe the plan for managing, storing, sharing, and preserving data generated during the research.

EpiDentLatvia targets the urgent oral health challenge in Latvia, where nearly all 12-year-olds are affected by dental caries. The project aims to generate evidence using traditional statistics and machine learning to identify risk factors, predict dental service needs and map inequalities in access. By analysing national and research datasets, it will inform policies that support prevention-focused, equitable dental care in line with WHO and UN health goals.

The primary objectives of this DMP are:

1. **Data Collection and Standardisation:** Establishing protocols for collecting data on various risk factors affecting dental health, accessibility of dental services, and the impacts of treatment disruptions, while ensuring standardisation across datasets for meaningful analyses.
2. **Data Sharing and Open Science Commitment:** The project emphasizes transparency and reproducibility by sharing cleaned and anonymized datasets in FAIR-compliant repositories. This commitment encourages public participation and collaboration with policymakers, aiming to democratize research tools.
3. **Data Analysis and Security:** Safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of research data while implementing robust statistical techniques and machine learning methods for analysis, to identify trends, disparities, and predictive factors influencing oral health outcomes.
4. **Long-term Preservation:** Ensuring that all datasets can be accessed post-project completion for future research, policy formulation, and ongoing public health initiatives. This aligns with the overall goal of fostering a collaborative environment in oral health research.

Researchers:

Sergio Uribe (orcid:0000-0003-0684-2025)

Ilze Maldupa (orcid:0000-0002-5967-956X)

Organizations:

Riga Stradiņš University

Contact: Uribe Sergio (sergio.uribe@rsu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: RSU Internal and RSU with LASE External Consolidation

Grants: EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the Epidemiological Profile of Oral Health in Latvian Children and Adolescents

Project: EpiDentLatvia: Mapping the Epidemiological Profile of Oral Health in Latvian Children and Adolescents

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-04-30

4. Templates

Descriptions

RSU DMP Template

The EpiDentLatvia project aims to analyze national oral health data using statistical and machine learning methods to identify risk factors, predict service needs, and map access disparities in dental care.

The aims and research questions are:

1. **Identify Risk Factors for Early Childhood Caries:** What risk factors and behaviors are linked to early childhood caries in Latvia, and what is the benefit of machine learning in helping to identify vulnerable populations?
2. **Quantifying the Impact of Early Childhood Caries:** How does early childhood caries affect general anesthesia use for dental treatments in Latvia? Can predictive models identify high-risk patients? Is it possible to identify patients at risk of GA re-interventions?
3. **Evaluate the Accessibility of Dental Services:** How accessible are dental services in Latvia, and what disparities exist in service availability?
4. **Assessing Long-Term Effects of Dental Service Disruptions:** What long-term effects did COVID-19 dental service disruptions have on preventive and non-invasive treatments in Latvia? What is the effect of limiting public dental care on the community?
5. **Epidemiology of Oral Health in Adolescents in Latvia:** What is the oral health status of Latvian adolescents aged 12–15, and how do lifestyle and socioeconomic factors influence their oral health outcomes?

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The EpiDentLatvia project uses de-identified and anonymized data to support the identification of modifiable risk factors for early childhood caries, quantify the impact of untreated caries on general anaesthesia use, assess inequalities in access to dental services, evaluate the long-term effects of service disruptions, and profile adolescent oral health. These analyses directly address the project's objectives to inform preventive strategies and guide evidence-based health policy.

The data originates from existing national administrative health records (obtained under agreement from the National Health Service), and datasets previously collected by the research team. No new data from human participants will be collected; the project reuses and expands existing datasets (ECC, GA, COVERAGE, COVID, YOUNG).

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

The data will be useful to researchers and students in public health, dentistry, and health policy, both at Rīga Stradiņš University and other academic institutions. It will also benefit governmental organisations such as the Ministry of Health, public health agencies, and municipalities planning dental care services. Additionally, non-governmental organisations focused on child health and oral health promotion, as well as private sector actors in health service planning or insurance, may use the data for policy development, service evaluation, and research.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Aggregate data
- Clinical data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

800,000,000

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

Yes

1.2.5 If Yes, please indicate what dataset are you re-using?

Riga Stradins University dataverse

Trends in dental treatment under general anaesthesia for children in Latvia 2005-2020 - Dataset

<https://dataverse.rsu.lv/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.48510/FK2/LUUOMS>
id: 10.48510/FK2/LUUOMS, Type: doi

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata will be provided in a complementary .txt file describing variables, structure, and processing steps for each dataset.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

MeSH Keywords

<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- Codebook
- ReadMe file
- Software documentation

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Each dataset will contain, at least, this minimal readme file:

README Section: Overview of dataset purpose, structure, and use in the EpiDentLatvia project.

DESCRIPTION: Summary of dataset content, data sources, anonymization process, and file types (e.g., .csv for tabulated data, .Rmd for analysis scripts); Clear reference to the project objective linked to the dataset.

CONTACT: Name and email of the dataset author or data manager.

FILES AND FOLDERS: List of all associated files: raw data, cleaned subset, R scripts, codebook, and variable dictionaries.

PREREQUISITES: Instructions on how to recreate the analysis environment (software, folders, packages).

VARIABLE DICTIONARY (DATACODES): Detailed list of variables with names, descriptions, units, and coding schemes in both Latvian and English.

ABSTRACT: A concise summary of the dataset context, background, and key findings.

SOFTWARE AND PACKAGES USED: List of software (e.g., R version) and packages required for analysis.

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

CSV, HTML and R scrips in quarto format

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Web browser, text editor, and R

R

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.2.5 Other relevant remarks

We will use additional deidentified and anonymized datasets:

1. Identify Risk Factors for Early Childhood Caries: (Dataset ECC [not published yet]).
2. Evaluate the Accessibility of Dental Services: (Dataset COVERAGE [10.17605/OSF.IO/R9YA7]).
3. Assessing Long-Term Effects of Dental Service Disruptions: (Dataset COVID [not published yet]).
4. Epidemiology of Oral Health in Adolescents in Latvia: (Dataset YOUNG [not published yet]).

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Riga Stradins University dataverse

RSU Institutional Repository

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0

We will use the Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 4.0 license to ensure that the data and scripts are freely accessible, reusable, and adaptable by others, while requiring proper attribution and that any derivative works remain openly shared under the same terms.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

For as long the RSU Dataverse repository works

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Security
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

In RSU Dataverse long term preservation costs are covered by RSU

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

Riga Stradiņš University

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Sergio Uribe (orcid: [0000-0003-0684-2025](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0684-2025))

SU will be responsible for data management in the EpiDentLatvia project. His tasks will include organizing and cleaning datasets, documenting metadata, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, depositing data and scripts in open repositories

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

No

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Access to the data will be restricted to the project researchers (Sergio Uribe and Ilze Maldupa).

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

All data will be stored in a secure, shared cloud folder, accessible only with individual, password-protected accounts by SU and IM. No third parties will have access during the project period.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long term preservation and curation

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

The datasets used in the project contain no directly identifiable personal data. All data will be anonymized prior to analysis, and any potential identifiers (e.g., patient ID numbers) will be hashed to prevent re-identification. No sensitive or classified information will be processed. Data use complies with national legislation and agreements with the data providers. No ethical or legal obstacles are expected for data sharing in anonymized form.

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

No

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

No

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Pseudonymization

Powered by

